

SELF-VIDEO INSTRUCTIONS IN ENHANCING FOOD PROCESSING SKILLS OF TVL STUDENTS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 23

Issue 10

Pages: 1272-1280

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2231

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13352130

Manuscript Accepted: 07-20-2024

Self-Video Instructions in Enhancing Food Processing Skills of TVL Students

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Abstract

This study attempted to perceive the Self-Video Instruction in Enhancing Food Processing Skill of TVL Students of Cabibihan National High School. The pre-experimental method was utilized for the forty-five (45) students of Cabibihan National High School, Tagkawayan District 1, Division of Quezon, in this study a survey questionnaire instrument was used in the gathering of data. The significant findings are the following: The majority of the student-respondents in the study are female with an average age of 17 years old, with their parent's educational background secondary with an average income is around P10,000. Based on the student perception of social media applications, in terms of the Lesson Objectives, the procedures/application in making different product, and performance monitoring were "Highly Manifested" by the students. As for the student's performance in food processing, it was revealed that most students are approaching proficiency with grades from 80-91 above. The study revealed that used of self-video instruction is significantly related to all food processing skills in TVL students. However, the student's pre-test and post-test score revealed that there is no significant relationship between the performance of the student-respondents before and after use of self-video instruction. Video-based materials boost students' creativity and cooperation. Access to video can help motivate students and create a distinctive context for their learning experience.

Keywords: *self-video instruction, food processing skills, and performance application*

Introduction

In the realm of education, and for the betterment of the nation as a whole, ensuring the quality and excellence of learning is important. It's imperative for schools to produce quality graduates who can contribute to the social and economic facets of nation-building, thereby driving the country towards comprehensive development and advancement. Recognizing the inevitability of change, the Department of Education (DepEd) has embraced curriculum reform to enhance the Philippine Educational System. This comprehensive transformation aims to extend basic education from ten to twelve years, aligning with global standards, as currently, only three countries, including the Philippines, Djibouti, and Angola, maintain a 10-year program among the 193-member states of UNESCO.

The last decade has witnessed a tremendous expansion of the use of video for instructional purposes in both formal and informal educational contexts. Most universities propose as a standard service the recording and distribution of lectures primarily aimed at students who cannot attend classes because of professional or family duties, and also as a support for revision. In 2012, universities became notably enthusiastic, perhaps excessively so, about Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs), where video content plays a pivotal role in delivering course material along with supplementary documents. Despite this recent surge in interest, video remains a significant research focus, with older applications persisting in certain context.

These include educational documentaries for subjects that aren't easily demonstrated first hand, as well as practice-based videos showcasing techniques within their relevant contexts. The utilization of video in informal settings aligns with the flourishing of video streaming platforms such as YouTube. Over the past 15 years, advancements in technology have facilitated the easy recording, editing, and dissemination of video content over the internet, leading to the emergence of various new formats and professions, such as YouTubers, along with innovative business models. Within this vast array of video content, a significant portion is created with deliberate instructional objectives, ranging from scientifically explaining phenomena and demonstrating products or expert procedures (commonly known as tutorials) to analyzing movies or video games, among other examples. Remarkably, most internet video creators lack formal training in video production and instead hone their skills over time, largely through feedback from viewers, particularly those who garner substantial audiences. As this brief listing demonstrates, formal and informal settings differ in the "nature" of video they use, yet they tend to be more and more alike, with universities seeking to follow the trends in order to be attractive to the younger generation.

Education encompasses in teaching and enabling individuals to acquire knowledge, skills, values, beliefs, and habits within a community, typically within a formal school setting where educators employ various methods such as storytelling, discussions, training, and research to impart learning. While education commonly occurs under the guidance of teachers or educators, individuals can also engage in self-directed learning through autodidactic processes.

Any experiences that influence the way individuals think, feel, or behave may be regarded as educational, particularly when facilitated by a teacher. Research has shown that video technology, particularly in educational contexts, enhances social interaction, offers personalized learning environments, serves as a straightforward delivery platform, is highly portable, and empowers learners with the ability to pause and rewind their learning process (Beheshiti, Taspolat, Kaya, & Sapanca, 2018). In a study comparing different approaches to teaching cooking skills, focus groups concluded that video technology proved to be the most effective method for instructing college students in culinary techniques (Surgenor et al., 2017). However, the study did not assess the perceived improvement

in students' ability to independently prepare meals as a result of this method.

The profound impact of technology has significantly transformed the exchange of information and ideas between educators and students. Higher education institutions have actively adapted to technological advancements by implementing online learning platforms, instructional videos, and various digital teaching methods. Despite these innovations, the utilization of digital learning resources beyond software applications remains relatively limited, particularly in the Philippines. This study concentrates on the efficacy of instructional videos in facilitating the teaching and learning processes, specifically in the field of design education, and explores their effectiveness for students. This research aimed to assess the impact of self-video instruction on students' comprehension of food processing.

It stemmed from the ongoing advancements in education aimed at enriching students' knowledge. Educators and students increasingly turn to instructional videos to grasp and analyze concepts. The utilization of video resources is evolving to meet the demands of contemporary and future learners. While the incorporation of videos in teaching is not a recent development, this study proposed evaluating their effectiveness in fostering information literacy, utilizing a student survey to gauge the efficacy of video lectures.

Video based materials boost students' creativity and cooperation. Access to video can help motivate students and create a distinctive context for their learning experience.

Research Objective

The aim of this study is to know The Effectiveness of Self-Video Lessons and Output in Enhancing Food Processing Skills of TVL Students of Cabibihan National High School. Tagkawayan Quezon.

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher utilized the pre-experimental method in determining the Self-Video Instruction in Enhancing Food Processing Skills of TVL Students in Cabibihan National High School.

This research used to determine the casual impact of an intervention on its target population. In this design, the respondents exposed to a certain experimental factor. The experiment has two parts of test, pre-test before the intervention and post-test after the intervention. It is a form of research where the investigator has no control over the independent variable. It has designs in which the evaluators manipulate and control one dependent variable for the variation related to the manipulation of the dependent variable.

This study stated that the key reason for doing this research is to determine the effectiveness of self-video instruction in food processing. The method was helpful in determining which factors represented by the independent variables will affect the dependent variable.

Respondents

The population of this study was composed of forty-five (45) TVL students belonging to one section of Cabibihan National High School, Tagkawayan, Quezon. The study comprised twenty-four (24) male students and twenty-one (21) female students. The respondents in this study utilized the purposive sampling technique which the whole population of the students was present during the conduct of the survey instrument.

Procedure

The researcher makes lesson exemplar including activity, analysis, abstraction and application of the lesson and the Self-Video Instruction that show the different lesson in food processing the tools and equipment, the process of making different product in food processing to be able to increase the performance of TVL students in Food Processing.

The researcher first secured the letter asking for the school head and respondents' cooperation and honest response about the study to be undertaken and treated with confidentially. The letter was attached together with the teacher made assessment. The researcher also secures a letter of consent to the Head teacher and the adviser. And also inform the students that their answer strictly confidential and all the information provided by the students will be kept and secure and use only for the research purposes.

The researcher makes a lesson exemplar that contains the lesson proper from activity, analysis, abstraction and application. Using the self-video instructions, the teacher discussed and demonstrated the process of making different product in food processing. In the first part of the video, the tools, equipment and the safety precaution shown by the teacher to know how the tool and equipment used during the processed and also the used of Personal Protective equipment. In the second part of the Self-Video Instruction is the procedure on how to make the product. The researcher followed the step by step procedure to have an accurate and quality product in food processing. The researcher showed the processed to the students by using self-video instructions and let the students make their own product in their own way.

Data Analysis

The data gathered were subjected to the following statistical treatments for the interpretation and analysis of findings.

The frequency-percentage distribution, as well as weighted mean and standard deviation, were used for descriptive questions, which include the perception about the use of Self Video instruction in food processing.

To determine the significant difference in Food Processing performance of TVL students before and after the implementation of Self-Video Instruction used the t-test was employed.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the analysis and interpretation of the data gathered through the research instruments provided. It determined the self-video instruction in enhancing the food processing skill of TVL students. This study used the tables to present the analysed data.

Part I. Profile of the Respondents

This part presents data on the frequency and percentage distribution of the profile of the respondents of TVL Students of Cabibihan National High School, Tagkawayan Quezon. This includes age, gender, parent's occupation, and family income and previous grade in food processing.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents in terms of Age*

<i>Age</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
21-23	1	2.22
18-20	9	20
15-17	35	77.78
Total	45	100

Table 1 show that most age of TVL students of Cabibihan National High School is 15-17 years old with 35 or 77.78 percent, followed by 18-20 years old with 9 or 20.00 percent, and 1 or 2.22 percent with the age of 21-23. This result shows that the students in TVL are mostly composed 15-17 years old.

Table 2. *Distribution of Respondents in terms of Gender*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Male	24	53.33
Female	21	46.67
Total	45	100

Table 2 show that among the forty-five (45) respondents, twenty-four (24) or 53.33 percent are males and twenty-one (21) or 43.67 percent are females. This result shows that the population of respondents is mostly composed of Male.

Table 3. *Distribution of Respondents in terms of Occupation of Parents-Father*

<i>Occupation</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Farmer	31	68.89
Construction worker	5	11.11
Factory worker	6	13.33
Business man	3	6.67
Total	45	100

Table 3 shows the profile of the respondents in terms of occupation of parents-father. Among the forty-five (45) respondents most of them are farmer with 31 or 68.89 percent. Followed by factory worker with 6 or 13.33 percent, construction workers with 5 or 11.11 and last is business man with 3 or 6.67 percent. This result shows that most of the occupation of the respondents are farmer.

Table 4. *Distribution of Respondents in terms of Family's Monthly Income*

<i>Monthly income</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
20,001-above	3	6.67
15,001-20,000	3	6.67
10,000-15,000	39	86.67
Total	45	100

Table 4 shows the profile of the respondents in terms of family monthly income. Among the forty-five (45) respondents most of them have 39 or 86.67 percent, followed by (3) or 6.67 percent of respondents which have a family income of 20,000 and above and 15,000 -20,000. This result shows that most of the family income of TVL students' parents ranging from 10,000-15,000.

Table 5 shows that most previous grades in food processing of TVL students of Cabibihan National High School is 85-89 with 17 or 37.78 percent, followed by 75-79 with 15 or 33.33 percent, followed by 12 or 26.67 percent and 90-94 with 1 or 2.22 and for 95 above no student got. This result shows that most of the students in TVL have previous grades in food processing of 85-89.

Table 5. *Distribution of Respondents in terms of Previous Grades in Food Processing*

<i>Previous grades</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
95-above	-	0
90-94	1	2.22
85-89	17	37.78
80-84	12	26.67
75-79	15	33.33
Total	45	100

Part II. Perception Of The Students On Self-Video Instruction

This part shows data on the frequency and percentage of the TVL Student in food processing Respondent based on their perception in terms of Lesson Objectives, Procedures/application in making different processed food and performance monitoring.

Table 6. *Perception on Self-Video Instruction of TVL Students in Food Processing in terms of Lesson Objectives*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
The Self-Video Instruction includes lesson objectives that...			
1. is clearly stated and understood.	4.73	0.45	highly manifested
2. is attainable through various exercise provide that keep us engage.	4.73	0.50	highly manifested
3. are relevant to our mental and physical well-being.	4.80	0.40	highly manifested
4. Promote moral values.	4.76	0.48	highly manifested
5. are aligned with all the competencies need in our course.	4.71	0.46	highly manifested
Overall	4.75	0.28	highly manifested

Legend: 1-1.49 Not Manifested 1.50-2.49-less manifested 2.50-3.49- manifested in moderate extent 3.50-4.49- manifested 4.50- 5.00 Highly manifested

Table 6 portrays the student's perception of self-video instruction in terms of lesson objectives. The indicator "are relevant to our mental and physical well-being." has the highest mean of 4.80 with the verbal interpretation of "highly manifested." Furthermore, the indicator "promote moral values" gets the second highest score with a mean of 4.76 with a verbal interpretation of "highly manifested." The indicator "is clearly stated and understood and is attainable through various exercise provide that keep us engage" gets a mean of 4.73 with a verbal interpretation of "Highly manifested." Lastly, "are aligned with all the competencies need in our course." the lowest mean is 4.71 with a verbal interpretation of "highly manifested." The overall mean of students' perception of self-video instruction in terms of lessons objectives is 4.75, with a verbal interpretation of "highly manifested"

The table suggests, in line with Gezegin (2014), that the utilization of video material results in superior vocabulary learning outcomes in language classrooms compared to relying solely on audio materials. The observed impact of video usage on learning target expressions aligns with the positive expectations of this study. While exposure to various types of materials, such as spoken language, printed text, or visual information, can convey the same message, the comprehension of these inputs may vary depending on the context and the individual student. The findings of this study indicate that when utilized with appropriate materials, such devices can be beneficial for both teaching and learning. Additionally, Resurreccion (2014) supported the notion that incorporating video lessons led to improved performance among students in the analysis, synthesis, and evaluation levels of specific Physics lessons. Furthermore, the study by Mendoza et al. (2015) confirmed the effectiveness of video presentations in enhancing students' learning.

Table 7. *Perception on Self-Video Instruction of TVL Students in Food Processing in terms of Procedures/Application in Making Different Processed Food*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
The Self-Video Instruction includes Procedures/Application in making different processed food that...			
1. are informative and comprehensive way.	4.76	0.43	highly manifested
2. were stated in proper order that can be perform well.	4.67	0.52	highly manifested
3. inspired me to spend more time studying to acquire practical skills.	4.78	0.42	highly manifested
4. indicate or stress the value of safety and sanitation.	4.78	0.42	highly manifested
5. taught us to be innovative and creative.	4.71	0.51	highly manifested
Overall	4.74	0.22	highly manifested

Legend: 1-1.49 Not Manifested 1.50-2.49-less manifested 2.50-3.49- manifested in moderate extent 3.50-4.49- manifested 4.50- 5.00 Highly manifested

Table 7 portrays the student's perception of self-video instruction in terms of procedures/application in making different processed. The indicator "inspired me to spend more time studying to acquire practical skills and indicate or stress the value of safety and sanitation." has the highest mean of 4.78 with the verbal interpretation of "highly manifested." Furthermore, are informative and comprehensive way" gets the second highest score with a mean of 4.76 with a verbal interpretation of "highly manifested." The indicator "taught us to be innovative and creative" gets a mean of 4.71 with a verbal interpretation of "Highly manifested." Lastly, "were stated in proper order that can be perform well." the lowest mean is 4.67 with a verbal interpretation of "highly manifested." The overall mean

of students' perception of self-video instruction in terms of procedures/application in making different processed is 4.74, with a verbal interpretation of "highly manifested".

The table implies that According to Agluba (2021), enrolling Tech-Voc strands should be a primary concern because it improves students' academic performance. TLE and Tech-Voc teachers, in particular, must motivate students to continue their expertise in Senior High School. In this way, children can improve their technical skills and achieve positive outcomes in academics and social. Technology and livelihood education are essential for being a functioning member of society.

Table 8. Perception on Self-Video Instruction of TVL Students in Food Processing in terms of Performance Monitoring

The Self-Video Instruction includes Performance monitoring that.....	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. meets the expectation in line with the objectives	4.78	0.42	highly manifested
2. is more accurate and more effective way.	4.64	0.48	highly manifested
3. are found more accessible and timeless rather than traditional setting of teaching.	4.78	0.42	highly manifested
4. support task performance immediately by replaying the past lesson.	4.87	0.34	highly manifested
5. allow to improve the quality of understanding and facilitate performance in the learning process.	4.76	0.48	highly manifested
Overall	4.76	0.24	highly manifested

Legend: 1-1.49 Not Manifested 1.50-2.49-less manifested 2.50-3.49- manifested in moderate extent 3.50-4.49- manifested 4.50- 5.00 Highly manifested

Table 8 portrays the student's perception of self-video instruction in terms of performance monitoring. The indicator " support task performance immediately by replaying the past lesson." has the highest mean of 4.87 with the verbal interpretation of "highly manifested." Furthermore, "allow to improve the quality of understanding and facilitate performance in the learning" gets the second highest score with a mean of 4.76 with a verbal interpretation of "highly manifested." The indicator " are found more accessible and timeless rather than traditional setting of teaching and meets the expectation in line with the objectives " gets a mean of 4.78 with a verbal interpretation of "Highly manifested." Lastly, " is more accurate and more effective way." the lowest mean is 4.64 with a verbal interpretation of "highly manifested." The overall mean of students' perception of self-video instruction in terms of procedures/application in making different processed is 4.76, with a verbal interpretation of "highly manifested".

This outcome suggests that according to Hasan Khan (2019), incorporating subtitles gives each student the option to watch, listen to, or read each presentation. Videos stimulate and captivate students, fostering interest and sustaining it for extended durations, while also offering educators an innovative and efficient method to cover and deliver the necessary curriculum content.

Part III. Pre-Test And Post-Test Scores In Food Processing

This part shows data on the frequency and percentage of the TVL Student in food processing Respondent based on their Pre-test and Post-test scores in maintain tools and equipment, estimation and calculation, food processing and applying food safety and sanitation.

Table 9. Pre-test score of the Respondents in Food Processing

SCORES	Maintaning tool and equipment		Estimation and Calculation		Food processing		Applying food safety and sanitation		Remarks
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
9-10	5	11.11	-	-	-	-	1	2.22	Excellent
7-8	8	17.78	-	-	2	4.44	1	2.22	Very Good
5-6	10	22.22	9	20.00	8	17.78	4	8.89	Good
3-4	17	37.78	18	40.00	22	48.89	19	42.22	Fair
0-2	5	11.11	18	40.00	13	28.89	20	44.44	Poor
Total	45	100%	45	100%	45	100%	45	100%	

Legend: 1-2 Poor 3-4- Fair 5-6- Good 7-8 -Very Good 9-10- Excellent

Table 9 demonstrates the result of pre-test of the respondents in food processing. In terms of maintaining tool and equipment, it can be noted that 17 or 37.78 is the highest percentage of the students got the range score of 3 to 4 remark as "fair" followed by the 10 or 22.22 percent of the students with the range score of 5 to 6 that remark as "good". 8 or 17.78 percent of the students got the remarks "very good" with the range score of 7 to 8, 5 or 11.11 percent of the respondents got the remarks "excellent" with the range score of 9 to 10, and lastly, the range score 0 to 2 has 5 or 11.11 percentage of the respondents remark as "poor". The results showed that the pre-test of the TVL students have a fair understanding in terms of maintaining tool and equipment. In terms of estimation and calculation 9 or 20 percent of the TVL students got the range score of 5 to 6 that remark as "good", 18 or 40 percent of the students got the range score of 3 to 4 remarked as "fair" and lastly, 18 or 40 percent of the students got the range score of 0 to 2 remarked as "poor". This

means that the students should be learned in terms of estimation and calculation.

In terms of food processing, it can be noted that 22 or 48.89 is the highest percentage of the students with the range score of 3 to 4 that remarked as “fair”, followed by 13 or 28.89 percent of the students with the range score of 0 to 2 remarked as “poor”, 8 or 17.78 percent of the students with the range score of 5 to 6 remarked as “good”, 2 or 4.44 of the students got the least percentage with the range score of 7 to 8 remarked as “very good”. In terms of applying food safety and sanitation, 20 or 44.44 is the highest percentage of the students got the range score of 0 to 2 with the remark as “poor”, followed by 19 or 19.22 percent of the students got the range score of 3 to 4 remarked as “fair”. Lastly, 1 or 2.22 percent of the students got the range score of 7 to 8 remark as “very good” with same percentage of the students got the range score of 9 to 10 remark as “excellent”.

Table 10. Post-test score of the Respondents in Food Processing

SCORES	Maintaining tool and equipment		Estimation and Calculation		Food processing		Applying food safety and sanitation		Remarks
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
9-10	37	82.22	32	71.11	36	80.00	26	57.78	Excellent
7-8	7	15.56	1	2.22	7	15.56	12	26.67	Very Good
5-6	1	2.22	10	22.22	1	2.22	6	13.33	Good
3-4	-	-	2	4.44	1	2.22	1	2.22	Fair
Total	45	100%	45	100%	45	100%	45	100%	

Legend: 1-2 Poor 3-4 Fair 5-6 Good 7-8 Very Good 9-10 Excellent

Table 10 demonstrates the result of post-test of the respondents in food processing. In terms of maintaining tool and equipment, it can be noted that 37 or 82.22 is the highest percentage of the students got the range score of 9 to 10 remark as “excellent” followed by 15 or 15.56 percent of the students with the range score of 7 to 8 remark as “very good”, lastly 1 or 2.22 is the least percentage of the students got the range score of 5 to 6 remark as “good”. In terms of estimation and calculation, it can be noted that 32 or 71.11 is the highest percentage of the students got the range score of 9 to 10 remark as “excellent” followed by 10 or 22.22 percent of the students with the range score of 5 to 6 remark as “good”, 2 or 4.44 percent of the students with the range score of 3 to 4 remark as “fair”. Lastly, 1 or 2.22 is the least percentage of the students got the range score of 7 to 8 that remark as “very good”. This means that most of the students got the high score of the post-test in terms of estimation and calculation.

In terms of food processing post-test, it be noted that 36 or 80 is the highest percentage of the students got the range score of 9 to 10 that remark as “excellent”, followed by 7 or 15.56 with the range score of 7 to 8 remark as “very good”.

Lastly, 1 or 2.22 is least percentage of the students got the range score of 5 to 6 remark as “good” same of the percentage of the students with the range score of 3 to 4 that remark as "fair". In terms of applying food safety and sanitation, it can be noted that 26 or 57.78 is the highest percentage of the students got the score range of 9 to 10 remark as “excellent”, followed by 12 or 26.67 with the range score of to 8 that remark as “very good”, 6 or 13.33 with the range score of 5 to 6 remark as “good”. And lastly, 1 or 2.22 is the least percentage of the students got the range score of 3 to 4 remark as “fair”. This means that most of the TVL students got the high score of post-tests in terms of food safety and sanitation.

The result of Post-test score of the student show how self-video instruction helped to improve the performance of the students in food processing. Having this kind of instruction promote active learning from the video and enhance the skills of the students in food processing.

Table 11. Performance score of the Respondents in Food Processing

Performance score	Frequency	Percentage	Remarks
91-above	4	8.89	Excellent
89-90	4	8.89	
86-88	10	22.22	Very Good
83-85	22	48.89	Good
80-82	5	11.11	Fair
Total	45	100	

Table 11 shows that most of the Performance score in food processing of TVL students of Cabibihan National High School is 83- with 22 or 48.89 percent remarks as “good”, followed by 86-88 with 10 or 22.22 percent with the remarks as “Very Good”, followed by 5 or 11.11 percent with the remarks as “Fair” and 89-90 above with 4 or 8.89 with the remarks as “Excellent”. This result shows that most of the performance score students in TVL in food processing of 83-85.

Table 12. Show the result of Pre-test and Post-test score of food processing competencies in terms of Maintaining tools and equipment in pre-test with the mean 5.18, standard deviation of 2.36. Post-test with the mean of 9.40 and standard deviation of 1.01 with the T result of 11.840. followed by estimation and calculation pre-test result mean show 3.11 with the standard deviation of 1.47 and Post test score mean with 8.63 with the standard deviation of 1.48 and T result of 19.940. In processing food mean result in Pre-test of 3.44

with standard deviation of 1.56 and post test score mean of 8.91 with standard deviation of 1.38 and T result of 19.159. Lastly in applying food safety and sanitation mean result in Pre-test 3.04 of with standard deviation of 1.69 and post test score mean of 8.16 with standard deviation of 1.57 and T result of 17.628. the df result in maintaining tools and equipment, estimation and calculation, processing food and applying food safety and sanitation are same with 44 result. And the significant 2-tailed in maintaining tools and equipment, estimation and calculation, processing food and applying food safety and sanitation are same with 0.000 result.

Table 12. *Significant Difference between the Pretest and Post test Score of the Respondents before and after Using Self-Video Instruction*

Food Processing Competencies	Pre-Test		Post-Test		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation			
Maintaining Tools and Equipment	5.18	2.36	9.40	1.01	-11.840	44	0.000
Estimation and Calculation	3.11	1.47	8.62	1.48	-19.940	44	0.000
Processing food	3.44	1.56	8.91	1.38	-19.159	44	0.000
Applying Food Safety and Sanitation	3.04	1.69	8.16	1.57	-17.628	44	0.000

The result show significant difference in a various competency after having a pre-test and post test score. The result of Post-test score of the student show how self-video instruction helps to improve the performance of the students in food processing. Having this kind of instruction promote active learning from the video and enhance the skills of the students in food processing.

Table 13. *Significant Relationship between Student's Perception on Self-Video Instruction to the Performance in Food processing*

Self-Video Instruction	Performance
Lesson Objectives	-0.009
Procedures and application of making different processed food	-0.103
Performance monitoring	0.043

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 13 show the relationship of student's perception on self-video instruction in food processing. The data show that Self-Video Instruction in terms of Lesson Objectives has no significant relationship as shown by a value of -0.009. Followed by the Procedures and application of making different processed food indicating no significant relationship with a value of -0.103. lastly, there is no significant relationship of self-video lesson instruction on the student's performance in terms of Performance monitoring with the value of -0.043.

The data indicates that there is no significant correlation between self-video instruction and students' performance and perception. According to Zane Education (2016), educators should aim to engage and excite students in the hands-on learning process, with video being an instructional medium that captures greater interest compared to traditional printed materials. Video combines sight and sound, making it particularly effective for auditory or visual learners. It stimulates and engrosses students, sustaining their interest for extended durations, while also offering educators an innovative and effective method to cover and deliver the required curriculum content.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the used of self-video instruction in teaching, has improved the performance of the students in the post-test score. Hence, the hypothesis in this regard is not sustained.

However, it was revealed that the use of self-video instruction has no significant relationship with the student's performance in the second quarter grade. Therefore, the hypothesis in this study is not supported by evidence and therefore sustained.

The following are recommended based on the study's findings and the conclusion drawn.

The school administrator may give new opportunities and teaching strategies by using self-video instruction or any kind of strategies that suit for the 21st-century learner and acquire the necessities for the students to improve their learning competencies.

Teachers teaching T.L.E. subjects or any subject may consider using self-video instruction as instructional tools for teaching TLE subjects for the improvement of student's performance. This is so since it resulted significantly in the students gaining skills based on their perception. It will also help the teacher enhance their teaching strategies.

This study also suggests other methods and strategies for teaching in the 21st century. This may enhance their technological skills in

I.C.T., TLE, and other subjects.

Future researchers may carry out these studies to keep in touch with the new teaching methods using self-video instruction to gain food processing skills and to improve their competence in this field.

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